

Toward a revised checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies, hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)
Part V: Rationale and framework for the Lycaenidae (part II)

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Abstract

This second review of taxonomic and nomenclatural issues in Lycaenidae examines the status of family-group names in the light of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN), historical classification schemes, recent phylogenetic evidence, and current usage. Emphasis is placed on the classification of subfamilies and tribes, for which conflicts among older names, synonymies, and prevailing usage have required rigorous assessment under the Code.

The classification of all species within the genera and subgenera of the subfamily Polyommatae, excluding the tribe Polyommataini (which will be addressed in a future contribution), is critically reviewed and justified. Particular emphasis is placed on the generic classification of the tribe Scolitantidini, for which alternative taxonomic arrangements have been proposed and remain contentious.

Key words

Taxonomy — Checklist — Papilionoidea — Lycaenidae — Lycaeninae — Theclinae — Polyommatae — Polyommataini — Lampidini — Celastrini — Scolitantidini — Everini — Zizeerini — Azanini (tribe proposed) — Phengarina (subtribe proposed) — Palaeophilota (subtribe proposed) — *Leptotes* — *Cyclus* — *Azanus* — *Lampides* — *Cacyreus* — *Celastrina* — *Tarucus* — *Phengaris* — *Maculinea* — *Pseudophengaris* (genus proposed) — *Turanana* — *Pseudophilotes* — *Palaeophilotes* — *Scolitantides* — *Iolana* — *Glaucopsyche* — *Zizeeria* — *Zizina* — *Cupido* — ESU — *Cigaritis estherae* — *Lycaena heracleana* — *Satyrium vandalousica* — Western Palearctic.

Introduction

The present article aims to clarify and justify the classification adopted in the checklist for the subfamily Polyommatae of the family Lycaenidae, with the exception of the tribe Polyommataini, which will be treated in a subsequent paper. Despite extensive taxonomic and phylogenetic research, the internal classification of Lycaenidae remains only partially resolved. In particular, the rank and delimitation of the major lineages traditionally recognised as subfamilies have been interpreted differently by various authors, reflecting differences in the morphological, molecular, and combined datasets on which their conclusions are based. As a result, alternative classifications continue to coexist in the literature, and some aspects of the higher-level taxonomy of the family remain subjects of ongoing debate.

Over the past decades, numerous phylogenetic studies have advanced competing hypotheses concerning the relationships among these groups. Analyses based on morphological characters, molecular data, or combinations of both have yielded alternative arrangements of the major clades and have often assigned them different taxonomic ranks, recognising them either as subfamilies or as tribes within more inclusive classifications. As a consequence, no single classification has gained universal acceptance, and the circumscription, placement, and relationships of several groups remain subjects of ongoing debate. In addition, some recent phylogenetic studies have proposed generic delimitations based primarily on molecular evidence, with limited consideration of morphological, ecological, biogeographical, or nomenclatural criteria. Although such approaches have provided valuable insights into evolutionary relationships, they may also contribute to nomenclatural instability when taxonomic changes are introduced without sufficient integration of other lines of evidence.

1. Classification of of tribes, subtribes, genera and subgenera within the subfamily Polyommatainae

1.1 Introduction - Taxonomic approach adopted in the present work

Recent phylogenetic studies have considerably improved our understanding of evolutionary relationships within the subfamily Polyommatainae. However, the translation of phylogenetic hypotheses into a practical and stable taxonomic classification remains a matter of debate. In several instances, the strict application of monophyly as the primary criterion for generic delimitation has led to the synonymisation of long-established genera or to the transfer of numerous species between genera. While such changes may reflect inferred evolutionary relationships more accurately, they can also result in substantial nomenclatural instability and reduce the continuity and practical utility of traditional classifications.

The classification adopted herein is guided by three complementary objectives: (1) the recognition of monophyletic taxa, (2) the explicit representation of the principal evolutionary lineages recovered by recent phylogenetic studies, and (3) the preservation of nomenclatural stability whenever compatible with the preceding objectives. The aim is to achieve a classification that reflects current knowledge of phylogenetic relationships while maintaining a practical and stable taxonomic framework.

In some cases, the recognition of previously unnamed monophyletic clades may require the establishment of new suprageneric taxa. However, such changes are generally limited in scope and have a considerably smaller impact on nomenclatural stability than the widespread synonymisation of genera. Another potential drawback of extensive generic synonymisation is the loss of diagnosability. Although the resulting genera may satisfy the criterion of monophyly, they may become morphologically heterogeneous and difficult to characterise using traditional taxonomic characters. In some instances, no clear diagnostic features remain other than those derived from molecular data, and species exhibiting markedly different external morphology, genital structures, or biological traits may be placed within the same genus. While such classifications may accurately reflect phylogenetic relationships, they can reduce the practical and descriptive value of generic taxa for taxonomists, ecologists, and conservation biologists.

The advantages of this approach are illustrated by two well-known cases within the subfamily Polyommatainae. The synonymisation of *Maculinea* under *Phengaris* and the placement of *Palaeophilotes* within *Pseudophilotes* have resulted in substantial nomenclatural changes, despite the recognition of clearly distinct evolutionary lineages. By making fuller use of intermediate taxonomic ranks, particularly tribes and subtribes, and, where appropriate, subgenera, it becomes possible to accommodate phylogenetic evidence without unnecessarily suppressing long-established generic names.

The classification proposed in the present work should therefore be regarded as a compromise between phylogenetic accuracy and nomenclatural stability. Its primary objective is not merely to assign names to clades but to provide a hierarchical framework that remains both informative and practical for future taxonomic, faunistic, and conservation studies.

It should be emphasised that the classification proposed herein is intended as a provisional framework based on currently available phylogenetic evidence. Ongoing phylogenomic initiatives and future large-scale studies will undoubtedly provide a more detailed understanding of relationships within the subfamily Polyommatainae and may necessitate the revision of some of the taxonomic arrangements adopted in the present work.

In particular, initiatives such as the Lepidoptera Tree of Life project (PSYCHE), which aim to generate extensive genomic datasets across the diversity of Lepidoptera, are expected to clarify relationships among several currently unresolved lineages. Consequently, the classification proposed herein should not be regarded as definitive, but rather as a practical and phylogenetically informed working hypothesis that can be readily updated as new evidence becomes available.

1.2 Historical and taxonomic context

The suprageneric classification of the Polyommatainae has undergone substantial changes over the past decades, reflecting the transition from morphology-based systems to phylogenetic hypotheses inferred from molecular data.

In his influential classification of the Lycaenidae, Eliot (1973) recognised four tribes within the Polyommatainae: Candalidini, Lycaenesthini, Niphandini, and Polyommataini. The first three tribes include relatively few genera and species and are not represented in the West Palaearctic fauna. In contrast, Polyommataini comprises a large number of genera and species, most of which occur in the Palaearctic region. To facilitate their classification, Eliot subdivided Polyommataini into several informal sections corresponding to limited groups of genera, which may be regarded as equivalent to subtribes. These sections were primarily defined on the basis of morphological characters, including wing venation, external morphology, and genital structures.

Restricting his study to the European and North African fauna, Higgins (1975) proposed a different arrangement, dividing the Polyommatainae into six tribes. The genera were distributed as follows:

Lampidini: *Tarucus*, *Syntarucus* (= *Leptotes*), *Cyclurius*, *Lampides*.

Everini: *Azanus*, *Cupido*, *Everes*.

Zizeerini: *Zizeeria*.

Scolitantidini: *Pseudophilotes*, *Scolitantides*, *Glaucopteryx*, *Maculinea*, *Iolana*, *Turanana*.

Celastrini: *Celastrina*.

Subsequent catalogues largely followed Higgins's arrangement, with only minor modifications. Vives Moreno (1994) placed *Cacyreus*, a genus not yet established in the European fauna at the time of Higgins's work, within Lampidini and recognised a separate tribe, Tarucini, for *Tarucus*. Leraut (1997), on the other hand, transferred *Celastrina* to Everini.

Since then, numerous phylogenetic studies have investigated the relationships among Polyommatainae genera, leading to several alternative classifications. Two recent large-scale phylogenetic analyses, one focused on the European fauna (Wiemers *et al.* 2020) and the other based on worldwide sampling of Papilionoidea (Kawahara *et al.* 2023), provide particularly useful frameworks for evaluating the suprageneric classification of the group.

Wiemers *et al.* (2020) presented a comprehensive phylogenetic hypothesis for the European butterfly fauna. Although the authors did not propose a formal tribal classification within Polyommatainae, their phylogenetic tree reveals several well-supported lineages corresponding to the following assemblages:

- A: *Azanus*
- B: *Zizeeria, Tarucus*
Celastrina, Lampides, Cacyreus
Phengaris
Scolithantides, Praepilotes, Iolana, Glaucopteryx
Turanana, Pseudophilotes
- C: *Leptodes, Cyclyrius*
- D: *Tongeia, Cupido*
- E: Polyommata

In contrast, Kawahara *et al.* (2023), based on a much broader worldwide sampling, recognised three tribes within the Polyommatae: Lycaenesthini, Niphandini, and Polyommataini. The first two tribes contain only a limited number of genera and are absent from the West Palaearctic fauna. The large tribe Polyommataini includes the majority of West Palaearctic taxa and is structured as follows:

- A: *Azanus*
- B: *Cupido, Tongeia, Luthrodes*
- C: Polyommata
- D: *Leptodes, Cyclyrius, Cacyreus, Lampides*
- E: *Pseudophilotes, Turanana*
Phengaris
Scolithantides
Iolana, Glaucopteryx
- F: *Celastrina*
- G: *Zizina, Zizeeria*
Tarucus

1.3. Conclusion

As higher taxonomic ranks are intended to reflect different levels of relationship within a phylogenetic framework, the subfamily Polyommatae is herein subdivided into several tribes. The alternative approach, consisting of recognising only three tribes, with Lycaenesthini and Niphandini containing relatively few species and Polyommataini encompassing the vast majority of taxa, greatly limits the ability of expressing phylogenetic relationships through lower-ranking subdivisions. Such a classification fails to adequately reflect several well-supported lineages revealed by both morphological and molecular studies.

Based on the phylogenetic evidence currently available, it remains premature to propose a definitive suprageneric classification of the subfamily Polyommatae. Nevertheless, several recurring patterns emerge from the studies discussed above and provide a basis for the following provisional arrangement.

Azanus consistently appears as part of a distinct lineage associated with several non-West Palaearctic genera. As no currently available tribal name appears suitable for this group, the genus is provisionally assigned to **Azanini** (proposed tribe).

Cupido and *Tongeia* are closely related genera and are therefore placed in **Everini**. Although their precise position within the subfamily remains uncertain, both recent phylogenetic studies recover them near the core Polyommataini lineage. To maintain monophyletic groups, *Luthrodes* is provisionally excluded from Everini and treated together with Polyommataini; its placement will be discussed in a subsequent paper.

Leptodes and *Cyclyrius* on the one hand, and *Cacyreus* and *Lampides* on the other, form two closely related pairs of genera. Wiemers *et al.* (2020) recovered these pairs as relatively distant lineages, whereas Kawahara *et al.* (2023) placed them within a common clade. Pending further phylogenomic studies, these four genera are provisionally grouped within **Lampidini**.

All recent phylogenetic studies consistently recover *Pseudophilotes*, *Turanana*, *Phengaris*, *Scolithantides*, *Iolana* and *Glaucopteryx* as closely related genera. They are therefore assigned to **Scolitantidini**.

The position of *Celastrina* remains particularly uncertain. Wiemers *et al.* (2020) recovered the genus close to *Lampides*, whereas Kawahara *et al.* (2023) placed it within a distinct clade together with numerous non-Palaearctic taxa. Pending further studies, *Celastrina* is provisionally retained within a separate tribe, **Celastrini**.

Finally, *Zizina*, *Zizeeria* and *Tarucus* form a well-supported lineage and are consequently grouped within **Zizeerini**.

The classification proposed herein, recognising a relatively large number of tribes within the Polyommatae, is fully compatible with the principle of monophyly as inferred from the phylogenetic hypothesis of Kawahara *et al.* (2023). It also provides a practical framework for recognising subtribes grouping closely related genera.

A limitation of several recent classifications is the synonymisation of numerous traditionally recognised genera, which are consequently reduced to subgeneric rank. The broader use of the intermediate rank of subtribe, as adopted herein, makes it possible to retain these genera while simultaneously preserving monophyletic suprageneric groups. As demonstrated in the following chapters, this approach reduces unnecessary nomenclatural changes and contributes to a more stable and informative classification.

1.4. Proposed tribe Azanini

This tribe-level lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree *A Time-Calibrated Global Phylogeny of Butterflies* by Kawahara *et al.* (2023), between:

BN003936_KD94S033_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Neolucia_agricola

and
BN007150_DL18S337_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Danis_danis

The limits and diagnosis of this lineage remain provisional and should be refined by future phylogenomic studies before any formal nomenclatural action is undertaken.

Type genus: *Azanus* Moore, 1881.

Currently included genera: *Neolucia*, *Sahulana*, *Theclinesstes*, *Azanus*, *Petrelaea*, *Pseudonacaduba*, *Orthomiella*, *Una*, *Ionolyce*, etc.

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2. *Phengaris* Doherty, 1891 and *Maculinea* Eecke, 1915 (Lycaenidae): nomenclatural and taxonomic considerations

2.1. Historical Taxonomic Framework and Phylogenetic Evidence

Prior to 2007, all Palearctic species of this group, including *alcon*, *nausithous*, *teleius*, *arion* and related taxa, were traditionally assigned to the genus *Maculinea*. This genus was characterised by a relatively homogeneous external morphology, notably the predominantly blue coloration of the male upperside and the characteristic arrangement of markings on the brownish underside. In contrast, the Oriental and eastern Palearctic species, including *daitozana*, *atroguttata* and *albida*, were assigned to the genus *Phengaris*, whose species share a distinct habitus characterised by a pale to whitish dorsal surface and a characteristic arrangement of ventral markings on a whitish underside.

In a phylogenetic study of the group, Fric *et al.* (2007) concluded that *Maculinea* and *Phengaris* should be treated as a single genus. Their proposal was based primarily on the principle of monophyly. Molecular analyses indicated that the species traditionally assigned to *Maculinea* did not form a lineage distinct from *Phengaris* but rather were embedded within the same evolutionary clade. The resulting phylogenetic hypothesis can be summarised as follows:

A + (B + C)

where:

A = *Maculinea alcon* + *rebeli*

B = *Phengaris daitozana* + (*atroguttata* + *albida*)

C = (*Maculinea nausithous* + *teleius*) + *arion*

Under this hypothesis, the recognition of *Maculinea* and *Phengaris* as separate genera would render one of the genera paraphyletic.

The phylogenetic study of Ugelvig *et al.* (2011) produced a somewhat different topology. In this analysis, the species traditionally assigned to *Maculinea* formed a more homogeneous lineage and were not intermingled with the species assigned to *Phengaris*. Furthermore, the genus *Caerulea* was recovered as part of the same broader clade, according to the following structure: In contrast, Kawahara *et al.* (2023), based on a much broader worldwide sampling, recognised three tribes within the Polyommatinae: Lycaenesthini, Niphandini, and Polyommadini. The first two tribes contain only a limited number of genera and are absent from the West Palaearctic fauna. The large tribe Polyommadini includes the majority of West Palaearctic taxa and is structured as follows:

A + (B + (C + (D + E)))

where:

- A = *Azanus*
- B = *Cupido*, *Tongeia*, *Luthrodes*
- C = Polyommatina
- D = *Leptodes*, *Cyclyrius*, *Cacyreus*, *Lampides*
- E = *Pseudophilotes*, *Turanana*
Phengaris
Scolithantides
Iolana, *Glaucoopsyche*
- F = *Celastrina*
- G = *Zizina*, *Zizeeria*
Tarucus

2.2. Taxonomic Interpretation and Provisional Classification

Pending the availability of such data, and following the principles outlined in the previous chapter, *Maculinea* is provisionally retained as a distinct genus in the present checklist. Together with *Phengaris* and *Caerulea*, it is assigned to the new subtribe Phengarina (subtribe proposed) within the tribe Scolitantidini.

Under the phylogenetic hypothesis proposed by Ugelvig *et al.* (2011), the maintenance of monophyletic genera would nevertheless require the recognition of an additional generic entity corresponding to clade B. Should this topology be confirmed by future studies, the resulting classification would comprise four genera arranged as follows:

A = *Caerulea*; B = *Pseudophengaris* (genus proposed); C = *Phengaris*; D+E = *Maculinea*.

Such an arrangement would preserve both the monophyly of all recognised genera and the long-established usage of the generic name *Maculinea*, while minimising nomenclatural changes within the group.

2.3. Proposed subtribe Phengarina

This subtribe-level lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree *A Time-Calibrated Global Phylogeny of Butterflies* of Kawahara *et al.* (2023), defined as extending from: BN004046_FH05M001_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Caerulea_coeligena and BN006335_AD00P068_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Phengaris_nausithous

This lineage belongs to the tribe Scolitantidini, which in the same phylogeny corresponds to the clade spanning from:

BN003925_AS92Z401_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Euphilotes_enoptes

to

BN002858_LEP31611_Lycaenidae_Polyommatinae_Polyommadini_Glaucoopsyche_lygdamus

The limits and diagnosis of this lineage remain provisional and should be refined by future phylogenomic studies before any formal nomenclatural action is undertaken.

Type genus: *Phengaris* Doherty, 1891. Currently included genera: *Caerulea*, *Phengaris*, *Maculinea*, etc.

Currently included genera: *Caerulea*, *Phengaris*, *Maculinea*, etc.

The subtribal groupings proposed herein are intended as provisional classificatory units that reflect current phylogenetic hypotheses. Their circumscription and diagnostic characters remain incompletely resolved, and the descriptions provided should not be interpreted as formal diagnoses. Additional phylogenetic, morphological, and biological evidence will be required to establish stable limits and comprehensive diagnoses for these lineages. Consequently, the proposed subtribal names are introduced only as provisional frameworks for discussing evolutionary relationships and remain subject to revision as new data become available.

2.4. Proposed genus *Pseudophengaris*

This genus lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree of Ugelvig *et al.* (2011) for the species *Phengaris daitozana* Wileman, 1908.

Type species: *Phengaris daitozana* Wileman, 1908.

Currently included species: *Phengaris daitozana* Wileman, 1908.

The genus-group classifications proposed herein are intended as provisional units to facilitate interpretation of currently available phylogenetic hypotheses. They do not constitute formal diagnoses under the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). The limits, composition, and diagnostic characters of several lineages remain insufficiently resolved and will require further phylogenetic, morphological, and biological study before robust diagnoses can be established. Accordingly, the proposed genus-group names are provided as practical tools for discussing phylogenetic relationships and should be regarded as provisional pending future systematic revision.

2.5. References

2.5. References

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3. *Pseudophilotes* Beuret, 1958 and *Palaeophilotes* Forster, 1938 (Lycaenidae): nomenclatural and taxonomic considerations

3.1. Phylogenetic context and taxonomic conflict

Zhang *et al.* (2023) conducted a detailed phylogenetic study of the tribe Scolitantidini. Their results revealed a very low genetic divergence (approximately 2.1%) between *Palaeophilotes triphysina*, the type species of *Palaeophilotes* Forster, 1938, and *Pseudophilotes baton*, the type species of *Pseudophilotes* Beuret, 1958. In contrast, *bavius*, traditionally assigned to the subgenus *Rubrapterus*, was recovered as a more distinct lineage within the same complex.

Based on these results, Zhang *et al.* (2023) concluded that the taxa traditionally treated as *Palaeophilotes* and *Pseudophilotes* should be regarded as congeneric. However, in view of the relatively rapid evolution of the nuclear genome and the phylogenetic structure recovered in their analyses, the authors proposed retaining *Pseudophilotes* and *Rubrapterus* as subgenera within *Palaeophilotes* rather than placing them in complete synonymy.

Although phylogenetically consistent, this solution would result in substantial nomenclatural changes, particularly through the replacement of the well-established generic name *Pseudophilotes* by *Palaeophilotes* for a number of widely known species.

An alternative approach is proposed herein. Rather than modifying the generic nomenclature, phylogenetic relationships may be expressed through the use of suprageneric ranks, particularly subtribes. Such an approach is difficult to implement in classifications recognising only a single West Palaearctic tribe, Polyommataini, because the extensive use of subtribes within such a broad taxonomic unit rapidly becomes impractical. However, the multi-tribal classification adopted in the present work provides a more suitable framework for the recognition of phylogenetically meaningful subtribes.

3.2. Nomenclatural Implications and Alternative Interpretations

An alternative approach is proposed herein. Rather than modifying the generic nomenclature, phylogenetic relationships may be expressed through the use of suprageneric ranks, particularly subtribes. Such an approach is difficult to implement in classifications recognising only a single West Palaearctic tribe, Polyommataini, because the extensive use of subtribes within such a broad taxonomic unit rapidly becomes impractical. However, the multi-tribal classification adopted in the present work provides a more suitable framework for the recognition of phylogenetically meaningful subtribes. Furthermore, additional molecular studies are still required. Several taxa closely related to this complex have not yet been adequately sampled, and their inclusion may significantly modify the inferred relationships. The phylogenomic tree published by Kawahara *et al.* (2023) already suggests that other genera may belong to the same evolutionary lineage. The phylogenetic placement of the genera *Euphilotes* and *Philotiella* remains uncertain. While Zhang *et al.* (2023) recovered these genera within the *Palaeophilotes–Pseudophilotes* clade in the mitochondrial tree, they appear as a distinct lineage in both the nuclear and chromosomal trees. Pending further investigations, this apparent incongruence should be regarded as unresolved and may have implications for the future classification of the group.

Pending the availability of more comprehensive phylogenetic data, *Palaeophilotes*, *Pseudophilotes*, *Rubrapterus* and *Turanana* are provisionally retained as distinct genera and placed within the new subtribe **Palaeophilotina** (proposed subtribe) of the tribe Scolitantidini.

The resulting phylogenetic structure may be summarised as follows:

A + (B + (C + D))

where:

A = *Turanana*

B = *Rubrapterus*

C = *Palaeophilotes*

D = *Pseudophilotes*

This arrangement preserves the monophyly of the group while minimising nomenclatural disruption and maintaining the long-established generic names currently used in the taxonomic literature. It also provides a flexible framework that can readily accommodate future phylogenetic results without requiring major changes to generic nomenclature.

3.3. Proposed subtribe Palaeophilotina

This subtribe-level lineage corresponds to the clade recovered in the phylogenomic tree *A Time-Calibrated Global Phylogeny of Butterflies* of Kawahara *et al.* (2023), defined as extending between:

BN001321_LEP50916_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Scolitantides_vicrama [= *Pseudophilotes vicrama*]

and

BN005598_RI18W078_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Micropsyche_ariana

This lineage is assigned to the tribe Scolitantidini, which in the same phylogeny corresponds to the clade spanning from:

BN003925_AS922401_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Euphilotes_enoptes

to

BN002858_LEP31611_Lycaenidae_Polyommatainae_Polyommataini_Glaucopsyche_lygdamus

The limits and diagnosis of this lineage remain provisional and should be refined by future phylogenomic studies prior to any formal nomenclatural action.

Type genus: *Palaeophilotes* Forster, 1938.

Currently included genera: *Turanana*, *Rubrapterus*, *Palaeophilotes*, *Pseudophilotes*, etc.

The subtribal groupings proposed herein are intended as provisional classificatory units designed to facilitate the interpretation of currently available phylogenetic hypotheses. They should not be regarded as formal diagnoses under the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). In particular, the limits, composition, and diagnostic characters of several lineages remain insufficiently resolved and will require further phylogenetic, morphological, and biological study before robust diagnoses can be established. Accordingly, the proposed subtribal names are introduced solely as practical tools for discussing phylogenetic relationships and are to be regarded as provisional pending future systematic revision.

3.4. References

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Zhang J., Cong Q., Shen J., Song L., Opler P.A. & Grishin N. V. 2023. Additional taxonomic refinements suggested by genomic analysis of butterflies. — *The Taxonomic Report of the International Lepidoptera Survey* 11(1) : 1-25, fig. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7604052>

4. Addition of Evolutionarily Significant Units (ESU) to the Checklist

4.1. ESU *Cigaritis estherae* Brévignon, 1985

Pending a more comprehensive integrative study of the entire group, *Cigaritis estherae* is provisionally regarded herein as an Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU), following the detailed study by Tarrier *et al.* (2026), which supported its recognition as a distinct species on the basis of biogeographical, biological, and mitochondrial genetic evidence, while also noting that the observed genetic divergence was relatively limited and subject to alternative interpretation.

Reference

Tarrier M., Brévignon C. & Gauthier J., 2026. Un nouveau statut pour une espèce endémique du Maroc : *Cigaritis estherae* Brévignon, 1984, n. stat. (Lepidoptera Papilionoidea : Lycaenidae : Aphnaeinae). — *Lépidoptères, revue des lépidoptéristes de France* 35(88): 3-12, fig. ([url not available](#))

4.2. ESU *Lycaena heracleana* (Blachier, 1908)

Pending further integrative taxonomic studies, the Moroccan populations currently assigned to *Lycaena alciphron heracleana* are provisionally regarded as a distinct Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU). This treatment is based on their mitochondrial genetic divergence (Dapporto *et al.*, 2022: [139, figs 255–256](#); Wiemers, 2003: [48, fig. 34](#)) and their marked geographic isolation from other *L. alciphron* populations, separated by more than 500 km.

References

Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodá R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022. The Atlas of mitochondrial genetic diversity for Western Palearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 00, 1–7. doi.org/10.1111/geb.13579 ([url Atlas appendix S1](#))

Wiemers M. 2003. Chromosome differentiation and the radiation of the butterfly subgenus *Agrodiaetus* (Lepidoptera: Lycaenidae: Polyommatus) – a molecular phylogenetic approach. — *Dissertation Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Fakultät der Rheinischen Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn*. 204 pp. ([url](#))

4.3. ESU *Satyrrium vandalusica* (Lederer, 1853)

The taxon *vandalusica* is here regarded as a potential Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU), based on the marked genetic divergence identified by Dapporto *et al.* (2022) within *S. spini*, between Spanish populations and those occurring elsewhere in Europe.

However, confirmation of this status will require further integrative research combining ecological and morphological evidence with higher-resolution genomic approaches, preferably based on whole-genome data.

Reference

Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodá R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022. The Atlas of mitochondrial genetic diversity for Western Palearctic butterflies. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. 00, 1–7. doi.org/10.1111/geb.13579 ([url Atlas appendix S1](#))

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

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